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The fall of the oil empire; A close joke with energy, a fact far from economics

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ABSTRACT

For years, there has been talk of ending energy resources in the world. Interestingly, even in 1914, this was discussed, and one of the American newspapers wrote that there were at most ten years left until the end of the world's oil reserves. Later, in 1939, the US Department of the Interior announced that there were only 13 years left until the end of oil reserves. In the last decade, advances in technology have led to more oil being extracted from oil fields, while high oil prices have made it harder for companies to find reserves that are more difficult to access. While there is still enough oil in well-known areas, forecasts show that the depletion of global reserves has led to more oil exploration.

Keywords: Oil, gas, coal, energy, oil depletion